

MODERN METHODS AND TECHNIQUES OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION.

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Abstract.

In this article, pre-school education in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the process, a great deal was given to modern methods of teaching foreign languages importance, and the modern teaching methods necessary to learn them included.

Keywords: foreign language in preschool education, Finnish teaching system, sign and picture method, sound recognition and matching method, learning with the natural world method, a method of adapting one's activities to students.

INTRODUCTION

Today, knowledge of foreign languages in a professional education is becoming one of the integral parts. This is also the process of pre-school education did not leave it aside. Teaching foreign languages during youth education importance has increased significantly. This is done by a religious scientist, candidate of historical sciences, senior teacher Natalya Kireva. "Either we prepare for life or exams. We will choose the first one", she emphasized. Recently, she spoke about the system and principles of education and why Finnish education is the best in the world shared their thoughts on what is considered as one of the good knowledge. Paying attention to pre-school education, social, economic and spiritual development is currently essential. I must also emphasize that in achieving success early childhood education from preschool specialists to help. There is a list of teaching strategies for the pre-school classroom. They give an opportunity to grow and learn as a teacher.

1. Method of working with characters and pictures.

According to Dr. Elaine Fogel Schneider, Director of International magazine, it is one of the ways to promote daily vocabulary. "It's about verbally labeling children with common brands and symbols." It is from the picture explains that translation helps to develop language. So this helps children learn new languages quickly and easily.

2. Voice recognition and matching method.

For this event, several large letters cut out of cardboard and you need a few small letters but not too big. For example, if your letters are C and E, and they are a cat and an elephant, you have to imitate a cat and an elephant. That means you should begin by telling the child the sound a cat makes. By this way, the child is encouraged to find something that starts with the sound and stick it to the letter. It is possible to keep decorated letters in the classroom or take home to share with parents. According to Schneider, this activity is a favorite among students, because it gives them practical help in the process of learning. In addition, they can create their own creates a "masterpiece".

3. A way to get used to the natural world.

Children are very interested in learning lessons in the natural environment. Usually, it is a great way to provide them with necessary information about the natural world in the backyard garden. This method may include to grow a plant from seed and it can provide not only information about them, but also help children to answer questions quickly and easily in a foreign language. This method relieves stress and also helps improve fine motor skills.

4. The method of adapting one's activity to students.

It can be difficult to follow teacher's plan in kindergarten. For this reason, for some children, this causes problems. Gretzinger says children from non-traditional homes can be more sensitive than other children. Teachers should be pay attention and think twice when they are asking children to draw pictures of their families, especially from an adopted child or the child whose parents have been divorced. Because they may feel lonely, sad or even angry. Therefore, it is necessary to think about their attitude.

5. With inclusive activities.

It may take a little longer to get involved, especially at the beginning of the year when you may not know all of your students, but if a child shows a sense of embarrassment, kindergarten teachers should pay attention to them individually. And also they should continue the creativity. It is considered that pre-school education is the first stage of education and upbringing of our youth. In fact, the preschool education program is unique to our children and it should help them grow and learn in an appropriate way. But children unlike adults, do not learn with the future in mind. In English the lesson should be held in the sense of "right here and right now". Children learn a foreign language more easily by understanding stories or winning games. If they want, they will strengthen the information they have learned through the games with their participation. On the one hand, the content should be related to children's life, on the other hand, the activities or tasks that you use should be interesting and important. Children see themselves as a part of the lesson and during the lessons, they behave and act like the hero of the play. In elementary grades, it will be effective and successful to learn foreign languages , if an activity is based on life situations and games. If a foreign language is taught through game-plot situations, all children willingly participate, because in this way they feel that they are a part of that situation. Pupils with a foreign language, first of all, "live" together in their rooms. Therefore, if communication is possible in the classroom, that must be in a foreign language. Children are limited to understanding not only instructions, but they can also express their needs through a foreign language. According to the constructive approach, children should know the meaning o the words and rules. Also, it helps to improve their critical thinking skills. Like all pupils, children have different learning styles. Tactic and kinesthetic learning styles require individual attention. In pre-school education, children's interests, talents are different. While you are teaching a foreign language, you are required to encourage and reward each child for their participation. You should help them to improve their acoustic, kinesthetic, rhythmic and visual skills. Children learn quickly, but unfortunately they forgot at once. Therefore, it will be helpful if you organize some activities and games to repeat the phrases and words learnt during the lesson. Teaching foreign languages requires different kinds of methods and ways.

First of all, we should make children pay attention to the content of the language and importance. Teaching successfully is related to the usage of the methods and techniques. We should give activities in which children must revise the learnt things during the lesson.

Communication is important to develop language skills. Socializing also helps to use the language in an effective way.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that the role of pre-school education is important to bring up our children. To do this, we are required to provide them with modern technologies and equipments. Pre-school education is also important to make children love their country and serve to the country's future. That is why we teach our children from a young age. While teaching foreign languages, we attract their attention with various interesting games. Our regular encouragement is the foundation for their future learning. We will not be mistaken if we say that this will be a step.

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